

The Silent Power of LGBTQ+ Visual Art in Shaping Indian Pop Culture

Yachana Singh

Research Scholar

Department of Drawing & Painting

University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, Rajasthan (India)

Dr. Amita Raj Goyal

Head & Associate Professor

Department of Drawing & Painting

University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, Rajasthan (India)

Abstract

Visual art in India has been a subtle yet potent channel for LGBTQ+ expression. It has helped in shaping attitudes of society and challenging dominant norms. LGBTQ+ visual art has consistently been a powerful force that is often under-acknowledged in shaping public consciousness and pop culture narratives in India, varying from ancient temple carvings to contemporary street murals and digital illustrations.

Long before same-sex desire could be openly acknowledged in mainstream media or public discourse, queer Indian artists have been, quietly and persistently, creating images that has given expression to individual identity and connected fragmented communities by sparking new ways of seeing. Artists like Bhupen Khakhar, Sunil Gupta, and newer collectives such as the Aravani Art Project and Fearless have shown that queer stories deserve to be seen in public spaces, on walls, in magazines, and galleries.

Unlike cinema or literature, which are subject to formal censorship and commercial constraints, art can circulate informally through bold murals in city, gallery shows, social media, and community spaces, often flying under the radar while reaching broad audiences.

The paper argues that queer visual art has contributed significantly to expand cultural representation of LGBTQ+ identities in India and foster public empathy while it navigates challenges of institutional exclusion and censorship. This research also blends academic insight with the deeply personal, adopting a qualitative, interdisciplinary approach that is rooted in queer theory, cultural studies, and visual analysis, also identifying key figures and movements, and analyse how these visual works operate through the frameworks of queer theory and visual culture. In doing so, we foreground the "silent power" of art that has been under-recognized yet has become vital force in Indian pop culture landscape. Thus, this paper explores how queer visual art in India has helped to shape the country's cultural and emotional imagination around gender and sexuality through art works.

Key word: Visual arts, Communities, Identity, sexuality, LGBTQ+.

Introduction

Indian popular culture has mostly stayed silent about LGBTQ+ lives for a long time. Until recently, television and movies rarely showed queer people in a real or respectful way. Instead, they were often shown as jokes or side characters. Public conversations about gender and sexuality were also limited or hidden, but queer voices have found other ways to be heard

beyond the news and movies. Many LGBTQ+ artists in India have used visual art to share their stories. They have expressed themselves through underground magazines, powerful murals, photography, gallery shows, and small handmade books called zines.

These artworks talk about love, desire, friendship, and the struggles of being queer in India. By doing this, artists are helping people understand LGBTQ+ lives better. They are also changing how we think about what Indian culture and imagery can be. These artists have played an important part in opening up minds and breaking old taboos in Indian society even though their role is often overlooked.

India's traditional art has long included themes of same-sex love and gender fluidity. The sculptures on the temples at Khajuraho show many forms of erotic love. During the Bhakti movement, poets wrote devotional poems where saints saw themselves as the "brides of God" (Dasgupta, 2012). These poems allowed same-sex feelings to be part of religious art. Scholar Ruth Vanita also explains that old miniature paintings often showed close and intimate friendships between women, sometimes suggesting romantic feelings. These examples show that Indian art once accepted many kinds of love and identity.

When British rulers brought Victorian laws to India the scenario changed. In 1862, they introduced Section 377, a law that made same-sex relations a crime. This law created shame and fear around LGBTQ+ lives for many years. India is only now starting to challenge this colonial mindset.

Earlier, queer art in India had to survive in hidden or coded ways. In the early 2000s, small groups of artists and activists made underground magazines (zines). They used Indian symbols and styles to include queer themes which allowed people to talk openly but safely. The first registered gay magazine, Bombay Dost (started in 1990), was sold wrapped in brown paper to protect its readers. Even with little money or reach, these efforts built a strong and supportive network across the country.

Literature Review

Some of the Indian Queer theories offer insights on how gender and sexuality were or have been seen in Indian history. Amara Das Wilhelm explains that old Indian texts recognized people who did not fit into male or female roles. They were described as *tritiya-prakriti* or "third nature," which gives a historical base for today's queer identities. Similarly, Vanita and Kidwai's book *Same-Sex Love in India* shows that same-sex love existed in precolonial times. This proves that queerness is not something new or foreign to Indian culture.

Madhavi Menon adds that in Indian culture, desire is often fluid and doesn't always fit into fixed labels like "gay" or "straight." She argues that love and intimacy often go beyond such categories.

However, studies about LGBTQ+ themes in Indian art and media are quite recent. Scholar Christopher has done important work on "artivism", a mix of art and activism. She says queer art in India works in two ways:

1. It shows personal stories, helping people understand queer lives.
2. It builds a sense of community and encourages public conversations.

According to Christopher, both types of art challenge social rules. Personal art helps humanize queer people, while public art like murals and performances breaks down the "us vs. them" divide in society.

Mukhopadhyay's research supports this view. She studied artists like Bhupen Khakhar, Dayanita Singh, and Arpita Singh, who quietly questioned traditional ideas of family,

community, and nationhood. Their art created space for queer themes, even within mainstream institutions. Khakhar's gentle images of gay male couples challenged the usual nationalistic and gender rules.

Other studies connect these ideas to changes in media and law. Gauram and Dugaje explain how British colonial rule brought negative ideas about homosexuality to India. As a result, Hindi films have often shown queer characters as jokes or villains. Because films are tightly controlled by dedicated boards and other parties, portrayal liberty there is very low. In contrast to that, independent art has played a more important role in changing attitudes.

Psychological research also shows that making art helps queer people feel better. A 2024 study by Motwani found that LGBTQIA+ adults in India who made art regularly felt more positive and mentally strong, even in a society that often excludes them.

From all this, we see two key roles of queer art in India:

1. It helps queer people see themselves and feel accepted.
2. It helps the public question outdated beliefs through symbolic and public art.

While much research focuses on film and writing, queer visual art in India is still a growing field. This study builds on what others have found and focuses on how visual art, like paintings, murals, and design has helped change public thinking. The research shows that Indian culture has long had space for queer identities, and today's queer artists are using that history to fight back against homophobia. What still needs more attention is how *visual* art (not just words or laws) has quietly shaped public awareness. This study tries to explore that by looking at key artworks, exhibitions, and media.

Methodology

This study uses a qualitative and interdisciplinary method. It looks at ideas and meanings rather than numbers, and it brings together different fields like queer theory, visual culture studies, and cultural sociology.

The focus is on how LGBTQ+ visual art in India, not including film, has influenced popular culture. The study looks at art shared through less formal spaces, such as:

- Street murals
- Zines (small, self-published magazines)
- Art gallery shows
- Digital illustrations, especially those shared on social media (like Instagram)

Historical Legacy of Queer Imagery

In ancient India, art and stories from mythology often showed fluid ideas of gender and sexuality. This can be seen in paintings, sculptures, and temple carvings. Famous temples like Khajuraho, Konark, and Rajarani include images of same-sex intimacy (Dasgupta, 2012; Mehrotra, 2021).

Historians like Amara Das Wilhelm, Ruth Vanita, and Saleem Kidwai have collected examples from many Indian texts, both old and new, that talk about same-sex desire. The perspectives presented in these texts vary widely, ranging from negative and neutral to often playful or celebratory. This proves that queer expressions were part of Indian culture long before colonial times, challenging the false idea that homosexuality came only from the West (Dasgupta, 2012).

These early artworks and writings created a rich visual language for showing queer desire. But this changed during British rule.

When the British ruled India, they brought strict moral rules, like Section 377 of the Indian Penal Code (1860), which made same-sex relationships illegal and shameful. British scholars often treated Indian texts like the Kama Sutra as strange and exotic but removed any open references to same-sex desire from public discussion.

Because of this, visual art during the colonial period rarely showed queer themes. A few artists still gave subtle hints. For instance: Amrita Sher-Gil, in the 1930s, painted scenes of close female relationships. Tyeb Mehta used unclear or suggestive body language in his paintings that some interpret as queer (Halder, 2024).

However, such themes stayed hidden or symbolic, reflecting the “colonial puritanism” of the time (Dasgupta, 2012).

Pioneering Artists and Movements to Contemporary Scenes

After India became independent in 1947, laws like Section 377 (against same-sex relations) remained in place. But the art world slowly started being more liberal. From the 1980s to 1990s, more artists began to show queer themes in their work.

One of the most important artists was Bhupen Khakhar (1934–2003), a self-taught painter from Baroda. He is often called India’s first openly gay artist and a pioneer of Pop Art in India (Mukhopadhyay, 2017). His famous painting *You Can’t Please All* (1981) (see Figure 1) shows a naked man on a balcony, seen as Khakhar’s way of “coming out” (Standley, 2017). His other works, like *Two Men in Benares* and *Yayati*, openly show male-to-male intimacy. He became well-known worldwide and his art was a form of public resistance against shame and silence (Christopher, 2024).

Figure 1

You Can’t Please All (1981)

Oil paint on canvas, 69 × 69 inches. By Bhupen Khakhar.

Source: <https://brooklynrail.org/2017/02/artseen/Bhupen-Khakhar/>

At the same time, Sunil Gupta, a Delhi-born photographer, used his camera to tell the stories of gay men in India. His photo series *Exiles* (1987) (see Figure 2) shows gay Indian men in Delhi at a time when it was not safe to be openly gay. Many models had their backs turned to the camera. Still, these images brought queer love into public view, pushing against society’s silence (Amin, 2024).

India Gate
Even if you have a lover you should get married
and have children. Who would look after you in
old age?

Figure 2

“*India Gate*” from the series *Exiles* (1987) by Sunil Gupta.

Source: <https://www.sunilgupta.net/exiles1.html>

Since the year 2000, there has been a lot of openly LGBTQ art in new and different forms of media. Indian popular culture, like films, ads, and digital content, is increasingly including more LGBTQ themes, and visual artists play a big role in this change.

For example:

- Tejal Shah (b. 1979), from Mumbai, makes videos and installations about South Asian queer identity. Her work *What Are You?* (2006) (see figure 3) tells the stories of transgender (hijra) sex workers in Mumbai’s red-light district (Havmoeller, 2010), (Archive, 2017).
- Kalki Subramaniam, a transgender artist and activist from Tamil Nadu, makes digital art and bright acrylic paintings. Her show *Shattered Silence* (2025) used both hand-made and AI-generated images to talk about trans rights, including job and education reservations (Rose, 2025).
- Jaishri Abichandani, an Indian-American artist, mixes Hindu religious art styles with modern queer subjects. Her artwork *Two Boys in Saris* (2018) (see figure 5) shows queer Muslim artists dressed like Hindu idols, blending religion and modern identity (Recinos, 2020).

Figure 3

What Are You? (2006) by Tejal Shah

Source: <https://aaa.org.hk/en/collections/search/library/tejal-shah-what-are-you>

Figure 4

Artwork by Kalki Subramaniam (photo by Liliya Rose)

Source: <https://www.newindianexpress.com/cities/kochi/2025/Jan/30/kalkis-shattered-silence-is-a-scream-for-empowering-trans-community>

Figure 5

Two Boys in Saris (2018) by Jaishri Abichandani, (Photo by Eva Recinos)

Source: <https://hyperallergic.com/718945/jaishri-abichandani-flower-headed-children-craft-contemporary/>

From the 2010s onward, collectives and community projects have helped make queer voices even more visible.

One great example is the Aravani Art Project, started in 2016 in Bangalore by artist Poornima Sukumar. It's a street-art group led by trans women and cis women. The group paints large, colorful murals in public places across South India. These murals show trans heroes, symbols with rainbow colors, and messages of pride. They aim to change how people see LGBTQ people and make public spaces safer. One artist said they are "reclaiming public spaces which were once unsafe for the trans community" (Prasad, 2023).

Figure 6

Shanthi Muniswam, Joythi H, and Karnika Bai of Aravani Art Project posed in front of their mural, Diaspore (2024) (photo by Vivienne Chow)

Source: <https://news.artnet.com/art-world/trans-artists-center-stage-venice-2470469>

In the world of zines (small magazines), the first Indian LGBTQ magazine, *Bombay Dost*, was founded by Ashok Row Kavi in 1990. It was distributed quietly at first but gave a strong platform for queer stories and art. Other zines like *Astitva* and *Gay Bombay* followed. These often used traditional erotic art styles, like the carvings of Khajuraho, to express queer identity in a subtle way (Hiremath, 2025).

Figure 7

Masala Mix Double Issue Cover. *Bombay Dost* Volume 5 No 2 & 3 (1996)

Source: <https://www.printmag.com/publication-design/underground-ink-indias-queer-magazines/>

In the digital age, a new generation of illustrators and cartoonists openly depict same-sex love and non-binary themes. Instagram and zine culture (e.g. *Do You See Us?* exhibits, Gaysi community art) have given them platforms (Aradhya, 2023). New media artists and illustrators create vibrant queer art that circulates online, often highlighting love, resilience and queer history (M, 2023). Artists like Priyanka Paul (@artwhoring) use illustrations to challenge gender roles and societal expectations, while Param Sahib (@parambanana) employs vibrant art to depict the everyday lives of gay Sikh men, offering rare representation. Opashona Ghosh (@iconsaredead) addresses queer love, mental health, and taboo subjects, and Anwesh Sahoo (@the.effeminare) explores gender as a spectrum. Veer Misra (@veermisra) focuses on

intersectional queer bodies and mental health, and Anirban Ghosh (@anirban_ghosh) celebrates non-binary identities through art that blends feelings, puns, and social justice. Jasjyot Singh Hans (@jasjyotjasjyot) explores body image and identity, drawing from pop culture. (Singh, 2020)

Figure 8

Digital Artwork by Anwesh Sahoo

Source: <https://www.instagram.com/the.affeminare/p/BvG3Yn4hD8t/>

Figure 9

Digital Artwork by Jasjyot Singh Hans

Source:

https://www.instagram.com/p/BVcoYhLjWqB/?utm_source=ig_embed&ig_rid=4a8acd07-8462-4644-b4af-8ff67b269036&ig_mid=10BCE4F6-0394-44BF-AF36-AF12E5CFF902

Thematic Analysis

Using Ancient or Cultural Motifs in a Modern Context

One main theme in queer art is showing love, desire, and relationships that do not follow straight (heterosexual) norms. In ancient India, desire was seen as something more than just physical acts, it had many forms (Bhupinder Kour & Menon, 2025). Today's queer artists often use traditional symbols and old stories to connect their work to this rich history of inclusivity for love and sexuality.

Modern graphic artists and textile designers sometimes use images from the temples of Khajuraho, known for their erotic sculptures, to show that India once accepted sexual diversity. In the early 2000s, underground queer magazines often included these temple carvings or medieval paintings in their pages. This helped people quietly celebrate same-sex love while avoiding censorship (Hiremath, 2025). Many artworks also refer to the *Kamasutra*, an ancient Indian text that speaks openly about same-sex relationships. Historian William Dalrymple says Hindu temples often challenge Western beliefs about religion and sexuality (BBC, 2014). This shows that queer identity in India has deep roots and is not something brought from the West. This challenges people who say queerness is "un-Indian."

Artist Bhupen Khakhar used every day Indian scenes to show queer love. In his painting *Two Men in Benaras* (1982), he shows two men living together in a regular Indian home. This helps make queer love seem normal and familiar. Scholar Sayantan Mukhopadhyay says that Khakhar's work shows many different ways sexuality can be imagined in Indian art. Even in his later paintings, less sexual and more about daily life, there are still quiet signs of queer love. Simple things like teacups, saris, or street signs in his paintings carry hidden meanings.

Mukhopadhyay (2022) compares Khakhar with photographer Dayanita Singh, who takes pictures of women in Kolkata. Her work also shows the deep bonds between people who don't fit traditional gender roles. Both artists challenge the male-centered ideas of Indian nationalism by focusing on private moments of care and connection.

Even folk art has been transformed by queer artists. In Kolkata, artist Uttam Chitrakar (born 1985) updated the old Kalighat painting style by showing gay and transgender people in his work. He replaced the usual "Babu-Bibi" (man-woman couple) with "Babu-Babu" or "Bibi-Bibi" (same-sex couples) (see figure 10) in his paintings (Fernando, 2021). His colorful, folk-style paintings have been shown at art fairs and even painted on city walls. This brings local cultural styles into queer storytelling and makes folk art part of India's growing queer culture.

Figure 10

The heteronormative "Babu-Bibi" has been replaced by "Babu-Babu" or "Bibi-Bibi" by Uttam Chitrakar. (Courtesy: Baro)

source: <https://indianexpress.com/article/lifestyle/art-and-culture/a-new-series-of-kalighat-pat-paintings-by-uttam-chitrakar-celebrate-gay-love-and-transpersons-7430597/>

Public Art and Protest

Public and community-based art is often used to make the lives of gay and trans people more visible. This kind of art helps create understanding between two groups: the LGBTQ+ community (called the "ingroup") and the rest of society that follows traditional ideas (the "outgroup"). Scholar Christopher calls this the "ingroup-outgroup" method, where art helps challenge social norms and reduce division. The goal is to start conversations, break down misunderstandings, and create a more inclusive society.

This happens through things like street murals, workshops, live performances, and online platforms. These forms of art invite everyone; queer and straight people alike, to take part, think, and talk. A strong example is a trans mural in Kolkata, curated by Nandini Moitra from the Fearless Collective, with the help of queer and trans artists (see figure 11).

Figure 11

Mural by Fearless Art collective on the walls of the Topcat CCU, Kolkata. (Photo credit: Jeet Sengupta)

source: <https://indianexpress.com/article/lifestyle/art-and-culture/a-silent-protest-this-80-foot-tall-mural-in-kolkata-shows-masculinity-through-the-transgender-persons-gaze-8943704/>

This mural is not merely for decoration. It boldly questions how people think about masculinity and trans men (Bandyopadhyay, 2023). Media outlets like *The Indian Express* praised the mural, calling it a “silent protest” that gets people talking about LGBTQ+ issues like fatherhood and emotional care, which are often wrongly seen as “only for straight men.”

Events like Pride festivals and art fairs also help spread queer stories. One such group is the Queer Arts Movement, India (QAM[I]), started by Romal Laisram. They hold art festivals where queer artists, filmmakers, and poets share their work. Laisram says many straight people who attend these festivals leave with more understanding and less prejudice after hearing queer voices (Patwardhan, 2017).

Queer art has even made its way into public protests and advertising. At the 2020 Mumbai Pride parade, queer graphic artists made hand-painted posters using Hindu mythology like Ardhanarishvara (a god who is both male and female) to demand equal rights and respect. Online platforms like Gaysi Family also create art and comics that both challenge Bollywood stereotypes and celebrate the real lives of queer South Asians.

These kinds of public and shared artworks support what Christopher found in his research: that queer “artists” (artist + activist) see themselves as bridges between LGBTQ+ communities

and the wider world. They bring queer images and stories into **galleries, online spaces like Instagram, zines, virtual art fairs, and major exhibitions**. For instance, artist and curator **Anita Dube** included many marginalized voices, including queer artists, when she curated the **2016 Kochi-Muziris Biennale**.

One important artist, **Sunil Gupta**, created a photo series called *New Pre-Raphaelites* (2008–09), showing young queer Indians in beautiful, romantic poses inspired by old paintings. These portraits showed a new generation of queer people ready to bring change. Gupta said his models were “impatient for change”, and many of them went on to organize India’s first Delhi Pride in 2008 and fight for legal rights. His art helps preserve the history of queer activism so others can see and remember it (Ray, 2019).

Coded Imagery

Because of persisting stigma and social pressure, much queer art in India has also used codes and symbols instead of being openly direct. Artists often use hindu temple motifs, archival photographs, or vintage Bollywood iconography to show queerness without using obvious modern gay symbols.

For example, **Bombay Dost magazine covers** from the 1990s showed silhouettes of gods or brides in wedding saris. These images seemed normal at first glance, but those who understood the culture could recognize them as subtle signs of queerness. Similarly, graphic artists often take **folk embroidery designs** and make small changes, like replacing peacocks with **rainbows** or writing **queer Hindi poetry** into traditional borders.

These hidden messages create a kind of “**secret history**” that only those in the LGBTQ+ community or allies might fully understand. As one article in **Underground Ink** explains, early gay zines in India celebrated queer identity with **soft, clever references** to Indian culture, fighting against norms without being loud or obvious (Hiremath, 2025).

Intersectionality: Caste, Class, and Gender

Along with talking about sexuality, queer art in India also talks about caste, class, and gender, especially how these parts of a person’s identity can add to their struggle.

One such example is the exhibition “**Vichitra Desh – Queer Nation**,” it showcased over 30 artists from different backgrounds, explicitly focusing on intersectionality and promoted conversations around gender and sexuality and also touching upon caste and class privilege, social injustice, and religious orthodoxy. These kind of exhibitions highlight how systemic oppression affects multiple marginalized identities simultaneously. (Sharma, 2023)

Another strong example comes from the artists of Bahujan queer community. For them the overlap of caste and sexual identity deepens feelings of marginalization. These artists more or less struggle to express themselves fully or receive acceptance in both mainstream and queer spaces. One key initiative supporting this cause is the **Dalit Queer Project**, it was started by Aroh Ankuth. This project uses social media and art to raise visibility and it creates a community for Dalit queer individuals. It also sheds light on the intersectional issues this group faces through art, poetry, stories, and other forms. (Wadhwa, 2024)

Platforms like **The Phosphene Magazine**, co-founded by non-binary Dalit artist Parth Pawar, exhibit artworks that explore the anxieties related to casteism and homophobia. They give a strong voice to these overlapping identities. But the widespread inclusion is still limited, and many continue to experience discrimination within queer movements. (Wadhwa, 2024)

Visual artists such as **Venkat Raman Singh Shyam**, who created the “*Ganja-Mahua Chronicles*,” (see figure 12) use traditional forms like Gond art to depict stories that merge

themes of queer desire and caste struggle, such as in the rebirth of lovers from different castes as anthropomorphic plants. This artwork boldly challenges conventional ideas of desire and pushes boundaries by addressing the deep-seated realities of the Indian caste system within the narrative of queer love (Bhupinderkour & Menon, 2025). These caste narratives are important for challenging the upper-caste dominance often seen in queer spaces, highlighting the necessity of acknowledging every aspect of an individual's identity.

Figure 12

Ganja-Mahua myth, Gond art by Venkat Raman Singh Shyam, Navayana, 2017

Source: <https://navayana.org/blog/2025/04/13/the-chronicle-of-ganja-and-mahua/?v=13b5bfe96f3e>

Transgender and Hijra Identities

Another key theme in Indian queer art is the representation of transgender and hijra (third-gender) identities.

According to researcher **Sayantana Mukhopadhyay**, many artists show **Ardhanari Shiva** (a god who is half man, half woman) or make portraits of hijra elders, combining Hindu and feminist symbols.

In 2014, India's **NALSA judgment** officially recognized a **"third gender,"** which supported what artists had been saying through their work, that **trans people have deep roots in Indian history.**

A more recent example is a **2022 photo series by Dayanita Singh**, showing a South Indian laborer, who was assigned male at birth, dressed in traditional women's clothing. The photo captures peace and strength, and connects to Tamil Nadu's **kothi subculture**, where gender is seen more fluidly. These artworks remind us that many gender identities have existed in India long before Western labels (Mukhopadhyay, 2022).

Results

LGBTQ+ visual art in India has brought about quiet but noticeable changes in public culture. These changes have mostly happened through informal and decentralized ways. Since visual art can be shared outside government-controlled spaces, it often reaches people more freely than cinema or literature, which face more censorship. This study finds that visual art, whether on city walls, in handmade magazines (zines), or shared on phones; has become a powerful way for queer people to express themselves and teach others. It has helped make queer presence and style a normal part of everyday visual life.

One major change is the increasing presence of queer images in public spaces. Art groups like the **Aravani Art Project** and the **Fearless Collective** have painted murals that show transgender and queer people in a positive and visible way. Unlike state-funded billboards or commercial art, these artworks are created by the community itself, often with queer people actively involved. They are self-authorized acts of representation that do not need official approval. These murals appear in parks, on footbridges, and in neighborhoods, helping people see queer lives regularly in public. As Christopher's study explains, these murals "take up public space and reach a wide range of people."

Another important change is the spread of queer themes through small, self-made magazines and digital art. Artists use platforms like Instagram, Facebook and other social media platforms to quickly share their work, without needing permission from editors, censors, or media companies. Many of these artists reuse traditional Indian images, like religious or folk art, and give them a queer twist. This creates a style that feels deeply Indian and boldly challenges social norms as well.

Most importantly, this widespread sharing of queer art is starting to change how Indian pop culture feels emotionally. As Stuart Hall says, pop culture is not just what people consume, it also includes what they dream about and imagine together. As people become more used to seeing queer symbols; like rainbow-colored Kalighat paintings, tender portraits of non-binary people, and scenes of queer families, they start to imagine LGBTQ+ life as something ordinary and beautiful. Even without too much capital or media coverage, queer artists have created a powerful new style that reshapes what feels possible. This change isn't sudden, but over time, it puts steady pressure on mainstream ideas, helping society slowly shift toward greater acceptance.

Discussion

The influence of LGBTQ+ visual art on Indian pop culture shows how creativity from the ground up can change public thinking, even without support from big institutions. This study shows that queer visual art is powerful because it works outside strict systems like those that control movies. Films need money, distribution, and approval from the government's film board. But visual art, like street murals, handmade zines, and digital posts only needs the desire to create and a place to share. This makes queer art both bold and strong.

In fact, being informal is what gives queer art its power. A mural on a bridge or a small, photocopied zine may not reach huge crowds, but it speaks to people in personal, unexpected moments. These experiences are direct and uncensored. They don't show queerness as something distant or dramatic, but as something real and human. Over time, they help people become more open-minded, curious, and emotionally accepting.

Because this kind of art is not made to make money or tied to the market, it is less exposed to commodification. Like, queer zines from the early 2000s were made for the community, not for profit. They could be raw, emotional, sexual, angry, or poetic. Today's digital queer illustrators similarly produce work without sponsorship. Their art often focuses on feelings, shared struggles, and personal stories that big media doesn't show. This helps Indian pop culture grow by adding new emotions and voices beyond the usual straight-centered ones.

This art also connects deeply with Indian roots. By using local myths, crafts, and symbols from before colonial times, queer artists show that gender diversity and same-sex love are not foreign ideas. They have always existed in Indian culture. This challenges conservative views and gives

pop culture a sense of queerness that is deeply Indian—blended, visual, and proud of its local identity.

In short, LGBTQ+ visual art is helping shape Indian pop culture through steady, everyday creative efforts. It doesn't need a stage or a spotlight. It works through walls, screens, and sketchbooks. Instead of trying to shock or entertain, it simply *exists*, again and again, until it feels normal. And that's how quiet images can make a big change.

Conclusion

This paper looked at how LGBTQ+ visual art in India affects pop culture and how people think, especially in the area of media representation. By studying different writings and examples, we showed that art is being used as a quiet but powerful form of activism.

We found that things like **murals, illustrations**, and other visual art forms help to:

- Make LGBTQ+ lives more visible
- Create empathy and understanding
- Challenge traditional ideas about gender and sexuality
- Start conversations between different communities

These art movements support the idea that art can bring social change. We believe that even though Indian LGBTQ+ art is often quiet or overlooked, it plays an important role in shaping how society sees queer people. It works alongside legal changes and activism by helping people imagine a more inclusive world.

For scholars and practitioners, this highlights the importance of including cultural analysis in discussions of LGBTQ rights and media. For now, we see that queer visual art in India is essential in building a society that is more open and inclusive to everyone.

Bibliography:

1. A Point of View: The sacred and sensuous in Indian art. (2014, April 4). *BBC News*. <https://www.bbc.com/news/magazine-26873149>
2. Amin, L. R. (2024, June 25). Sunil Gupta's Extended Queer South Asian Family. *Hyperallergic*. <http://hyperallergic.com/927594/sunil-gupta-hymns-to-queer-south-asian-life/>
3. Archive, A. A. (2017). Tejal Shah: What Are You? *Aaa.org.hk*; Asia Art Archive. <https://aaa.org.hk/en/collections/search/library/tejal-shah-what-are-you>
4. Asokan, R. (2019, April 1). Kochi-Muziris Biennale. *Artnews.com*. <https://www.artnews.com/art-in-america/aia-reviews/kochi-muziris-biennale-2-2-62661/>
5. Bandyopadhyay, A. (2023, September 13). Kolkata queer art gets "elevated" by 80-foot-tall mural celebrating trans men. *Telegraphindia.com*; *Telegraph India*. https://www.telegraphindia.com/my-kolkata/places/kolkata-gets-80-foot-mural-celebrating-trans-men-on-em-bypass/cid/1965940#goog_rewarded
6. Bhupinderkour, & Menon, M. (2025). Queer Representations in Indian Dalit Art works breaking Boundaries (Poetry, Cinema and Paintings). *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, 13(1), 68–73. <https://doi.org/10.35629/9467-13016873>
7. Blakely, R. (2023, June 9). India's first and only gay magazine tests taboos by making a comeback. *The Times*. <https://www.thetimes.com/travel/destinations/asia-travel/india/indias-first-and-only-gay-magazine-tests-taboos-by-making-a-comeback-53ch7f9dvj8?region=global>

8. Chow, V. (2024). Shanthi Muniswam, Joythi H, and Karnika Bai of Indian art collective Aravani Art Project posed in front of their mural, Diaspore. In News.artnet.com. <https://news.artnet.com/art-world/trans-artists-center-stage-venice-2470469>
9. Christopher, A. M. (2024). From Silence to Canvas: The Role of Artivism in Transforming Gender and Sexuality Norms. *Sexuality & Culture*, 29. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12119-024-10256-6>
10. Dasgupta, R.K. (2010). Queer Sexuality: A Cultural Narrative of India's Historical Archive.
11. Das, S. (2021). Gay Subculture and the Cities in India: A Critical Reading of Select Works of R Raj Rao. *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 13(3). <https://doi.org/10.21659/rupkatha.v13n3.40>
12. Das, S. (2023, September 18). A silent protest: This 80-foot-tall mural in Kolkata shows masculinity through the transgender person's gaze. *The Indian Express*. <https://indianexpress.com/article/lifestyle/art-and-culture/a-silent-protest-this-80-foot-tall-mural-in-kolkata-shows-masculinity-through-the-transgender-persons-gaze-8943704/>
13. Fernando, B. (2021, July 31). A new series of Kalighat pat paintings by Uttam Chitrakar celebrates gay love and transpersons. *The Indian Express*. <https://indianexpress.com/article/lifestyle/art-and-culture/a-new-series-of-kalighat-pat-paintings-by-uttam-chitrakar-celebrate-gay-love-and-transpersons-7430597/>
14. Gauram, B. S., & Dugaje, M. D. (2024). Representation of LGBTQIA in Bollywood Films. *Integrated Journal for Research in Arts and Humanities*, 4(2), 145–148. <https://doi.org/10.55544/ijrah.4.2.24>
15. Gupta, S. (1987). "India Gate " from the series Exiles. In sunilgupta.net. <https://www.sunilgupta.net/exiles.html>
16. Halder, M. (2024, March 26). Mapping the cultural footprint of the queer community in India. *Harper Bazar*. <https://www.harpersbazaar.in/culture/story/mapping-the-cultural-footprint-of-the-queer-community-in-india-938412-2024-03-26>
17. Havmoeller. (2010, January 24). Tejal Shah A Queer Feminist Artist From India | Feminine Moments. *Feminine Moments | Queer Feminist Art Worldwide*. <https://www.femininemoments.dk/blog/tejal-shah-a-queer-artist-from-india/>
18. Hiremath, J. (2025, January 28). Underground Ink: A Short History of India's Queer Magazines. *PRINT Magazine*. <https://www.printmag.com/publication-design/underground-ink-indias-queer-magazines/>
19. Kakar, S. (2013, December 19). A tradition of quiet tolerance. *India Today*. <https://www.indiatoday.in/magazine/cover-story/story/20131230-sudhir-kakar-supreme-court-verdict-on-section-377-gay-rights-769371-2013-12-19>
20. M. (2018, July 18). Queer Your Feed: 11 Desi-Queer Artists To Follow On Instagram - Gaysi. *Gaysi*. <https://gaysifamily.com/lifestyle/queer-your-feed-11-desi-queer-artists-to-follow-on-instagram/>
21. Mehrotra, D. (2021, June 29). The Pre-Colonial History of Homosexuality in India: Why Love Is Not Western - Academike. *Academike*. <https://www.lawctopus.com/academike/history-of-homosexuality-in-india/>
22. Menon, M. (2018). Infinite variety : a history of desire in India. *Speaking Tiger*.

23. Motwani, H. (2024). Art And Affect: Effect Of Art Creation On The Positive And Negative Affect In The Population Of India. Educational Administration Theory and Practices, 30(1). <https://doi.org/10.53555/kuey.v30i1.4998>
24. Mukhopadhyay, S. (2017). Dying breaths: Bhupen Khakhar, queerness, and late style (Doctoral dissertation, University of California, Los Angeles). UCLA Electronic Theses and Dissertations Repository. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/81j3m010>
25. Mukhopadhyay, S. (2022). Making worlds, making way: Queer belongings in Indian contemporary art (1980-2000) (Doctoral dissertation, University of California, Los Angeles). UCLA Electronic Theses and Dissertations Repository. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/04b1j1nw>
26. Patwardhan, A. (2017, April 29). How Art Is Breaking Myths & Stereotypes about India's Queer Community. The Better India. <https://thebetterindia.com/98234/the-queer-arts-movement-india-qami/>
27. Prasad, S. (2023, May 13). Aravani Art Project: A collective of "spider-women" creating safe spaces through art. The Indian Express. <https://indianexpress.com/article/cities/bangalore/aravani-art-project-a-collective-of-spider-women-creating-safe-spaces-through-art-8606374/>
28. Rao, R. R. (2017). Criminal love? : queer theory, culture, and politics in India. New Delhi Thousand Oaks, California Sage Publications.
29. Ray, A. (2019, April 16). LGBT Rights in India: What Does it Mean for Artists? ELEPHANT. <https://elephant.art/lgbt-rights-in-india-what-does-it-mean-for-artists/>
30. Recinos, E. (2022, March 22). South Asian and Modern Queer Aesthetics Merge in Visually Sumptuous Art. Hyperallergic. <http://hyperallergic.com/718945/jaishri-abichandani-flower-headed-children-craft-contemporary/>
31. Rose, L. (2025, January 30). Kalki's "Shattered Silence" is a scream for empowering trans community. The New Indian Express. <https://www.newindianexpress.com/cities/kochi/2025/Jan/30/kalkis-shattered-silence-is-a-scream-for-empowering-trans-community>
32. Sahoo, A. (2020). https://www.instagram.com/p/BxsNQehHXso/?utm_source=ig_embed&ig_rid=58c6475c-eb36-4c72-99f8-c8fbec45de38&ig_mid=7A700AB8-8611-4DE9-8F9B-D8472E4B99DE
33. Sharma, V. (2023, December 12). Queer Tales At Vichitra Desh - Queer Nation: A Conglomerate Of Queer Artists. Feminism in India. <https://feminisminindia.com/2023/12/12/queer-tales-at-vichitra-desh-queer-nation-a-conglomerate-of-queer-artists/>
34. Shyam, V. R. S. (n.d.). Ganja-Mahua Chronicles. In Navyana.org. <https://navayana.org/blog/2025/04/13/the-chronicle-of-ganja-and-mahua/?v=13b5bfe96f3e>
35. Singh, J. (2017). https://www.instagram.com/p/BVcoYhLjWqB/?utm_source=ig_embed&ig_rid=4a8acd07-8462-4644-b4af-8ff67b269036&ig_mid=10BCE4F6-0394-44BF-AF36-AF12E5CFF902

36. Singh, S. (2020, May 18). 10 Queer Indian Graphic Artists You Must Follow on Instagram - Gaylaxy Magazine. <https://www.gaylaxymag.com/articles/entertainment/10-queer-indian-graphic-artists-you-must-follow-on-instagram/>
37. Standley, M. (2017, February 1). Bhupen Khakhar You Can't Please All | The Brooklyn Rail. <https://brooklynrail.org/2017/02/artseen/Bhupen-Khakhar/>
38. Tejal Shah: What Are You? Exhibition catalog. (2006). Galerie Mirchandani + Steinruecke, Mumbai.
39. Vanita, R., & Saleem Kidwai. (2020). Same-sex love in India readings from literature and history. New York Basingstoke Palgrave.
40. Wadhwa, A. (2024, December 4). The Plight and Invisibility of Queer Bahujan Artists. NICKLED and DIMED. <https://nickledanddimed.com/2024/12/04/the-plight-and-invisibility-of-queer-bahujan-artists/>
41. Wilhelm, A. D. (2004). Tiritiya-Prakriti: People of the Third Sex. Xlibris Corporation.
42. Wong, T. (2021, June 28). 377: The British colonial law that left an anti-LGBTQ legacy in Asia. BBC News. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-asia-57606847>